

Attitude Of Safety Precautions to Hepatitis B Infection Among Health Care Workers in General Hospitals in Anambra State.

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Abstract

Health care workers in general hospitals are always faced with so many challenges which are commonly associated with infectious diseases like hepatitis B, and that is the reason the study determined the health care workers safety precautionary measures of hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra State. Four purposes and research questions guided the study while four null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The research design adopted for the study was a cross-sectional survey design; the area of the study was Anambra State. The population of the study comprised of 932 general hospitals in Anambra State. The sample size consists of 280 health care workers both male and female which was determined using Taro Yamane formula for a finite population the instrument for data collection was health care workers attitude towards safety Precautions of hepatitis B questionnaire (HCWsASPHBQ). THE Instrument was validated by three experts; the reliability was established using cronbach alpha (k-r20) and the reliability coefficients of Attitude and practice items were 0.65 and 0.74 respectively. The data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the Findings indicated that there was a positive attitude towards safety precautionary measures of hepatitis B infection. Conclusion and Recommendations were made based on the findings. There is need for continuous health education of health care workers in hospitals to sustain the positive attitude.

(Keywords: Hepatitis B, health care workers, Hospital).

Introduction

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is a highly infectious viral pathogen of public health concern. There are several different viruses that can infect your liver and cause inflammation (hepatitis). They include hepatitis A, B, C, D and E. Each is a little different in how they are transmitted, how they affect one's body and how they are treated (or prevented). Hepatitis B is the most common serious liver infection in the world. It is caused by the hepatitis B virus that attacks and injures the liver. Two billion people (or 1 in 3) have been infected and about 300 million

people are living with a chronic hepatitis B infection. Each year up to 1 million people die from hepatitis B despite the fact that it is preventable and treatable. The available report indicates that approximately two billion people are infected with HBV worldwide, with the majority in Africa and Asia (Amudalat et al, 2023) . Health workers are all people engaged in work actions whose primary intent is to improve health, including doctors, nurses, midwives, public health professionals, laboratory technicians, health technicians, medical and non-medical technicians, personal care workers, community health workers, healers and traditional medicine practitioners. The term also includes health management and support workers such as cleaners, drivers, hospital administrators, district health managers and social workers, and other occupational groups in health-related activities as defined by the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO-08) (WHO, 2024). Healthcare workers may be prone to infection this may be due to a lack of compliance with infection control recommendations from established guidelines such as the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (Sadoh, et al., 2006). Hand washing, glove use, and correct disposal of sharp instruments are all part of the CDC's recommended precaution, which is aimed to prevent the spread of blood-borne infections like HBV (Maamor et al, 2022).

Having enough proper attitudes toward the infection is crucial in preventing the occupational exposures. However, attitude, and practices regarding transmission of HBV infection and its preventive measures vary among HCWs and is evidently inadequate in most developing countries. The delivery of health care has the potential to transmit hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) to both health-care workers and patients. Outbreaks of HBV and HCV infection have occurred in outpatient settings, hemodialysis units, long-term-care facilities, and hospitals, primarily as a result of unsafe injection practices; reuse of needles,

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finger stick devices, and syringes; and other lapses in infection control. To prevent transmission of blood borne pathogens, health-care providers should adhere to recommended standard precautions and fundamental infection-control principles, including safe injection practices and appropriate aseptic techniques. Safety precautions are described as the state of being away from hazard caused by natural forces or human errors randomly (Selcuk, 2015). Safety precautions are meant to reduce the risk of transmission of blood-borne and other pathogens from both recognized and unrecognized sources. Standard precautions were proposed by the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) in the year 1996. It came after the review of the already existing concept of universal precautions (UP) defined as a set of precautionary measures designed to prevent transmission of HIV, HBV and other blood borne pathogens when providing first aid or healthcare services (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention cited in Nwoga, Ajuba and Omotowu, 2021). However, the aim of safety precautions safety precautions is to protect both the health care worker (HCW) from being infected and the uninfected patient from getting infected by the healthcare workers. However, the components of safety precautions as highlighted by Nwoga. et al (2021) includes proper hand hygiene after touching blood, body fluids, secretions, excretions, contaminated items, immediately after removing gloves and between patient contacts; use of personal protective equipment (PPEs) such as gloves, masks, goggles, face shield; soiled patient care equipment; environmental; textiles and; needles and others ; patient resuscitation; patient placement; respiratory hygiene/cough etiquette.

Although, the health workers are from time to time exposed to different seminars and workshops on various ways they can protect themselves from different dangerous communicable diseases in which hepatitis B virus is among them. No study known to the

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researchers has conducted a study on the study area and that is why this research was designed to determine attitude and practice of safety precautions to hepatitis B infection among health care workers in general hospitals in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine attitude of safety precautions to hepatitis B infection among health care workers in general hospitals in Anambra State. Specifically, the study determined;

1. Hand washing as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state.
2. Environmental control as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state.
3. The use of disposable as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B in general hospitals in Anambra state.
4. The use of protective devices as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B in general hospitals in Anambra state

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the attitude of health care workers on hand washing as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state?

2. What is the attitude of health care workers on environmental control as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state?
3. What is the attitude of health care workers on use of disposable as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state?
4. What is the attitude of health care workers on the use of protective devices as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of signifance;

1. There was no significant difference in the attitude on hand washing by health care workers as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state based on their gender
2. There will be no significant difference in the attitude on hand washing by health care workers as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state based on their years of experiences.
- 3 .There was no significant difference in the attitude on environmental control by health care workers as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state based on their gender.

5. There was no significant difference in the attitude on environmental control by health care workers as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state based on their years of experiences.

Methods

The research design to be adopted for this study is the cross-sectional survey design. The area of this study is Anambra State of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of all healthcare workers in Anambra State working in general hospital. They are all together 932 in the State. The estimated population of healthcare workers in all the general hospital on the State Ministry of Health records (2024). The sample size was 280 healthcare workers both male and female. This was determined using the 'Yaro Yamane' formula for a finite population. Multistage sampling was used to select the sample size of the study. The instrument for data collection for this study was a researcher developed instrument titled Healthcare workers attitude of safety measures of Hepatitis B questionnaire (HCWsASMHBQ). The data collected were checked for reliability using cronbach alpha measure of determining internal consistence for attitude questions the reliability coefficient was 0.74. The data collected was analyzed using statistical package for social science version 25 (SPSS). Means and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. The research hypotheses were tested using t- test analysis and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1

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What is the attitude of health care workers on hand washing as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state?

Table 1

Mean Attitude of Healthcare Workers to Handwashing as Safety Precautionary Measures towards Hepatitis B Infection

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Attitude to handwashing for hepatitis B prevention	266	16.62	2.55

Table 1 shows that the health workers’ mean attitude to handwashing as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection was 16.62. Since the value was greater than the 12.5 scale average, it was decided that health workers have positive attitude to handwashing as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection.

Research Question 2

What is the attitude of health care workers on environmental control as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state?

Table 2

Mean Attitude of Healthcare Workers to Environmental control as Safety Precautionary Measures towards Hepatitis B Infection

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Attitude to environmental control for hepatitis B prevention	266	14.39	2.66

The results presented in Table 2 indicate that health workers’ mean attitude towards environmental control as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection was

14.39. This implies that health workers have positive attitude to environmental control as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection.

Research Question 3

What is the attitude of health care workers on use of disposable as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state?

Table 3

Mean Attitude of Healthcare Workers to Use of Disposals as Safety Precautionary Measures towards Hepatitis B Infection

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Attitude to disposables for hepatitis B prevention	266	17.62	2.24

The results presented in Table 3 show that health workers’ mean attitude towards use of disposables as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection was 17.62. This value suggests that health workers have positive attitude to the use of disposables as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection.

Research Question 4

What is the attitude of health care workers on the use of protective devices as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection in general hospitals in Anambra state?

Table 4

Mean Attitude of Healthcare Workers to Use of Protective Devices as Safety Precautionary Measures towards Hepatitis B Infection

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Attitude to protective devices for hepatitis B	266	15.92	3.14

prevention

The results presented in Table 3 show that health workers' mean attitude towards use of protective devices as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection was 15.92. This value suggests that health workers have positive attitude to the use of protective devices as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection.

Discussion

Attitude of Health-care Workers on Safety Precautionary Measures towards Hepatitis B Infection.

The results of the study showed that; health-care workers have positive attitude to hand washing as a safety precautionary measures towards hepatitis B infection. Also, health-care workers have positive attitude towards environmental control as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection; health-care worker also have positive attitude towards the use of protective devices as a safety precautionary measure towards hepatitis B infection. The findings of the study was so because, before one becomes a health-care worker anywhere in the world, they are being taught how they should protect themselves against certain infection and they are also told the impact of not adhering to those precautions. Hand washing is a common easy and less expensive way of protecting one from diseases, infection and death. Health-care workers meet and threat so many patients at the same time so they engage in hand washing as a way to protect themselves, their family members and also the society hepatitis B is a very dangerous and highly infectious disease. So, health care workers need to practice this simple method of hand washing in order to protect them. The health-care workers also have good attitude toward environmental control like making sure that that environment is clean and free from toxic substance that would lead to infection. The health-care workers also make use of disposables that is items can be used ones and they have good attitude towards using them and also patients insist on health-care workers changing the

medical items used on them so this would automatically increase the health-care workers attitude towards the use of disposables in treatment and attending to patients. It would not be a surprise for health-care workers to have good attitude towards the use of protective devices because it is one of the ways in which the health-care workers are protected towards hepatitis B infection in their work place. The findings of the study were supported by the study done by Dwartama, et al (2022); they noted a high level of positive attitude toward hepatitis B infection.

The result was also not supported by the findings of Kabamba-Tshikongo et al (2023); that the HCSs had a terrible attitude towards hepatitis B infection. For the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the attitude of male and female HCW's towards hand washing the null hypothesis was rejected; also attitude towards environmental control among HCW's the null hypothesis was not rejected' for the use of disposables among male and female HCW's the null hypothesis was rejected also for the use of protective devices, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made;

The findings of the study showed that this health-care workers in general hospitals in Anambra State has good attitude towards safety precautionary measures of hepatitis B infection which includes; hand washing, environmental control, use of disposables, and use of protective devices. For practice of safety precautionary measure of hepatitis B infection, health care workers in general hospitals in Anambra State highly practice the hepatitis B safety precautionary measures; which in also include frequent hand washing immediate

environmental control, frequent use of disposable and regular use of protective devices in order to prevent spread and contraction of hepatitis B infection.

Recommendation

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made;

1. There is need for constant health education of the health care workers for them to sustain the good attitude and practice of safety precautionary measures of hepatitis B infection.
2. There is also need for patient educational on the safety precautionary measures of hepatitis B among patient in other to help the HCW's in controlling the spread of hepatitis B infection.
3. Health Education for the general public is also important with regards to hepatitis B infection, as it is a deadly disease so that another people who do not have he infection will know how to prevent the occurrence of such infection.

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